

SELF-CONCEPT AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE AS PREDICTORS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

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Self-Concept and Teaching Performance as Predictors of Emotional Intelligence

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Abstract

The study determined the level of self-concept and teaching performance as predictors of emotional intelligence of TLE teachers in Polomolok, South Cotabato. This study utilized descriptive-correlational design. The Slovin's formula was used to get the desired sample size of 124. Stratified sampling was utilized so that everyone had the chance to be part of the study and to represent each school-respondent. In analyzing the data, the mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation of Coefficient, and Multiple Regression Analysis were used. Based on the findings of the study, the level of self-concept of TLE teachers was high in terms of self-fulfilment, honesty, and emotional self-concept, while moderately high with regards to autonomy. Moreover, the level of teaching performance of TLE teachers was high in relation to the content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, assessment and reporting, community linkages and professional engagement, and personal growth and professional development, while moderately high in diversity of learners and curriculum and planning. Furthermore, the level of emotional intelligence of TLE teachers was very high in terms of social skills, while high in self-awareness, motivating oneself, and empathy while moderately high in terms of managing emotions. Additionally, there were significant relationships between self-concept and emotional intelligence, teaching performance and emotional intelligence of TLE teachers. Finally, the domain of self-concept that significantly predicted teachers' emotional intelligence was emotional self-concept. On the other hand, the domain that best predicted teachers' emotional intelligence regarding teaching performance was curriculum and planning.

Keywords: *educational management, TLE teachers, self-concept, emotional intelligence, teaching performance, philippines*

Introduction

Globally, teachers are increasingly struggling with challenges related to their emotional Intelligence, which significantly impacts their ability to manage stress and maintain a balanced approach to education. They face many pressures, including the need to cater to diverse learner needs, insufficient parental support, inadequate funding, overemphasizing standardized testing, negative public perceptions, shifting educational trends, the demands of modular distance learning, and overwhelming workloads. These issues collectively strain teachers' emotional resilience, often leading to difficulties in effectively managing their emotions and maintaining the mental well-being necessary for optimal teaching performance (Drigas & Papoutsi, 2018).

On the other hand, emotional Intelligence plays a vital role in education. Emotional Intelligence, often known as EI, is the capacity to recognize and manage their and others' emotions. People with high emotional Intelligence know how they feel, their emotions, and how their feelings affect others. Moreover, emotional Intelligence is a determining factor in occupational and professional education disciplines. If a teacher understands how to use emotional Intelligence, it can lead to a valuable life. Teachers must comprehend the distinction between cognitive and emotional Intelligence to achieve academic brilliance. However, they must also focus on their learners' emotional literacy, which will be shown when teachers assess their emotional literacy (Arghode et al., 2022; Turner & Stough, 2020).

As an emotionally intelligent teacher, the researcher demonstrates concern for her learners. The researcher establishes an emotional atmosphere in the classroom that fosters learner learning and assists the researcher in becoming more effective in ensuring academic success. Teachers' comfort, self-efficacy, and job happiness are influenced by their emotional Intelligence, which improves kids' social relationships. As a result, emotional Intelligence directly impacts how we teach and learn (Skordoulis et al., 2020).

When it comes to emotional intelligence, the ability to recognize, analyze, and regulate one's emotions and those of their students, public school teachers frequently encounter difficulties. One significant challenge is maintaining a positive and empathetic attitude despite the demands and stress of their profession. The researcher must navigate various emotional triggers, such as dealing with disruptive behavior, managing conflicts, and handling the pressure of high expectations from students, parents, and administrators. Additionally, the researcher encounters emotionally charged situations that require quick thinking and the ability to remain composed and supportive. It can be challenging for a teacher to balance one's emotional well-being while being attuned to their students' diverse emotional needs, making emotional Intelligence an ongoing area of growth and development in their teaching practice.

A notable research gap exists in understanding the interplay between self-concept, teaching performance, and emotional Intelligence (EI) among educators. While studies have explored the individual impacts of self-concept and teaching performance on EI, more research is needed examining how these factors collectively contribute to EI development in educational settings. Further investigation is needed to elucidate the specific mechanisms through which self-concept and teaching performance enhance or hinder EI among teachers, potentially informing targeted interventions and training programs to improve emotional competencies in educational

professionals.

Due to this, the researcher conducted this study to determine the self-concept and teaching performance as predictors of TLE teachers' emotional Intelligence in Polomolok, South Cotabato. The researcher wanted to determine the level of self-concept and teaching performance of teachers and how it affected their emotional Intelligence. This descriptive-correlation study aimed to determine the level of self-concept and teaching performance as predictors of emotional Intelligence of TLE teachers in Polomolok, South Cotabato.

Research Objectives

The study determined that self-concept and teaching performance are predictors of emotional Intelligence among TLE teachers in Polomolok, South Cotabato. Specifically, the following objectives were formulated:

1. To determine the level of self-concept among TLE teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. self-fulfillment;
 - 1.2. honesty;
 - 1.3. autonomy; and
 - 1.4. emotional self-concept.
2. To evaluate the level of teaching performance of TLE teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 2.2. learning environment;
 - 2.3. diversity of learners;
 - 2.4. curriculum and planning
 - 2.5. assessment and reporting;
 - 2.6. community linkages and professional engagement; and
 - 2.7. personal growth and professional development.
3. To assess the level of emotional Intelligence of TLE teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. self-awareness;
 - 3.2. managing emotions;
 - 3.3 motivating oneself;
 - 3.4. empathy; and
 - 3.5. social skills.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. self-concept and emotional intelligence of the teachers and
 - 4.2. teaching performance and emotional intelligence of TLE teachers.
5. To determine which domain in self-concept and teaching performance significantly predicts emotional Intelligence.

Methodology

This section presents the research design, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection procedure, the data analysis, trustworthiness, and ethical considerations employed in this investigation.

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative experimental research design. When doing quantitative research, closed-ended questions are usually preferable. Most of the time, only when given a pre-made list of possibilities can responders produce thoughtful, open-ended answers. This strategy will significantly increase the success of the quantitative research process compared to using open-ended, qualitative questions. It is more efficient because it does away with the need to spend much time coding several open-ended replies (Cooksey & Cooksey, 2020; Swart et al., 2019). Moreover, the goal of quantitative research design is to gather numerical data and extrapolate it to other demographics. With this design, every detail is well thought out and planned before data collection. The researcher also has a well-defined research topic that is being answered objectively. Data includes things like numbers and statistics. Projects can be used to look into causal linkages, forecast results, or, in a broader sense, generalize ideas (Ahmad et al., 2019; Rahman, 2020).

On the other hand, the descriptive survey method of research measures the association of variables with varying levels of measurement. Descriptive survey research design is a method used to gather information about a population or a specific group of people by asking them questions about their beliefs, opinions, behaviors, or experiences. This type of research design focuses on describing the characteristics of the sample rather than testing hypotheses or making predictions. It is frequently utilized in business and marketing research and social sciences, including psychology, sociology, and education. Descriptive surveys can be conducted through various means, such as face-to-face interviews, telephone surveys, mail surveys, or online surveys (Millner et al., 2020).

Participants

This study was conducted in Polomolok, South Cotabato. The respondents were 124 teachers from 3 different schools in Polomolok 1 district: 70 teachers from Polomolok Central Elementary School, 27 teachers from Eustacio Barcatan Elementary School, and 27

teachers from Eugenio L. Rañada Elementary School.

Slovin' Formula was utilized to get the desired sample from the total population. From 180 original respondents, there were only 124 teachers as the final population sample size. Slovin's formula is a statistical tool used to calculate the appropriate sample size for a survey, given a specific margin of error and confidence level. To further meet the requirements of students from indigenous communities, they modify and use culturally relevant teaching techniques. The formula states that the sample size required for a survey equals the population size divided by one plus the population size times the square of the margin of error (Tejada & Punzalan, 2012).

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents

Schools	Number of Respondent	
	<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>
Polomolok Central Elementary School	100	70
Eustacio Barcatan Elementary School	40	27
Eugenio L. Rañada Elementary School	40	27
Total	180	124

The researcher set the inclusion criteria for the study's respondents: male or female public school teachers ages 25-50 who were currently teaching at Polomolok Central Elementary School, Eustacio Barcatan Elementary School, or Eugenio L. Rañada Elementary School. Public school teachers who did not meet these criteria were not included as respondents. Conversely, certain individuals were excluded from participation in this study, including teachers aged below 24 and above 51. Additionally, respondents who were unable or unwilling to consent or cooperate in data collection were excluded from the study.

Nevertheless, respondents had the right to withdraw from the study at any stage without providing a reason. Any respondent who chose to withdraw was assured that their decision would not have any negative consequences or impact on their relationship with the school or program. Furthermore, if any respondent displayed discomfort, distress, or emotional unease during the study, appropriate measures were taken to support and ensure their well-being.

Instruments

Three sets of questionnaires were used in this study. The questionnaires were validated and attested by expert validators.

Questionnaire for Self-Concept of TLE teachers. This questionnaire was used to determine the level of self-concept of TLE teachers. It was adapted from the Structure of Personal Self-Concept (PSC) Questionnaire by Goñi et al. (2011). It had four indicators. The first indicator self-fulfillment, was made up of six statements. The second indicator honesty, with five statements. The third indicator autonomy, with five statements. Lastly, the fourth indicator, the emotional self-concept with six statements.

The five-point scale was used for the research variables. The Likert Scale asks respondents to check a box or leave blank answers to many questions about a stimulus, attitude, and object (Allen & Seaman, 2007). The number derived directly from a rating scale is supposed to be handled as measures by computing averages or, more broadly, any arithmetic operations.

The five orderable gradations to assess the level of self-concept with their respective range of means and descriptions are as follows:

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree	It means that the level of self-concept is very high
3.50-4.49	Agree	It means that the level of self-concept is high
2.50-3.49	Fairly Agree	It means that the level of self-concept is moderately high
1.50-2.49	Disagree	It means that the level of self-concept is low
1.0-1.49	Strongly Disagree	It means that the level of self-concept is very low

Questionnaire for Emotional Intelligence of TLE teachers. This questionnaire was used to determine TLE teachers' emotional intelligence levels. It was adapted from the (EI) Emotional Intelligence Questionnaires by Goleman (1995). It had five indicators: self-awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself, empathy, and social skills. Each indicator had ten statements.

The five-point scale was used for the research variables. Thus, the Likert Scale requires individuals to tick a box or blank in response to many items concerning an attitude, object, and stimulus. It is common to treat the number obtained from a rating scale as measurements by calculating averages or, more generally, any arithmetic operations.

The five orderable gradations to assess the level of emotional intelligence with their respective range of means and descriptions are as follows:

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree	It means that the level of emotional intelligence is very high
3.50-4.49	Agree	It means that the level of emotional intelligence is high
2.50-3.49	Fairly Agree	It means that the level of emotional intelligence is moderately high
1.50-2.49	Disagree	It means that the level of emotional intelligence is low
1.0-1.49	Strongly Disagree	It means that the level of emotional intelligence is very low

Questionnaire for Teaching Performance. This standardized questionnaire was used to determine the level of teaching performance of TLE teachers. It was based on the DepEd Order 2, s. 2015, the standardized Key Results Area (KRA) of Individual Performance Commitment a Review Form (IPCRF) for teachers. This instrument consisted of 5 indicators: content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, and factors. The teachers were instructed and guided to check the box according to the column appropriate to their choice, and all items should be answered. An attached sample of this instrument is in Appendix C.

Data Collection

After the approval of the panel members, the researcher undertook the following steps and procedures in gathering data for the study. The Graduate School of Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges and the Ethics and Review Committee granted the researcher permission to proceed with this study. Following approval, the researcher obtained a letter of authorization from South Cotabato's school division office and superintendent. Then, the researcher asked permission from the office of the Principal of Polomolok Central Elementary School, Eustacio Barcatan Elementary School, and Eugenio L. Rañada Elementary School to conduct the study on their elementary teachers. After clearance, a letter of recommendation was asked for so that the researcher could provide the study participants with the survey. When delivering the questionnaire to the participants, the researcher gave a description of the study tool and its purpose.

The researcher retrieved the survey forms once the respondents had completed all the questions. Finally, the researcher collated all of the data collected from the respondents depending on the study's sub-problems. The statistician was given the tallied data to analyze statistically. The statistical data was examined and interpreted. Conclusions were formed from the data, and recommendations were made based on the study's findings.

Ethical Considerations

Research ethics depend on this and are therefore essential to maintaining the integrity of science and upholding human rights and dignity, as well as science and society. The voluntary, informed, and secure participation of research subjects in studies is ensured compromises. The researcher strikes a compromise between following significant research objectives and adhering to moral research practices. It is always necessary to prevent permanent or excessive harm to respondents, whether unintentional or not.

Informed Consent. To allow respondents to fully understand the implications of their participation and make an informed, thoughtful, and free-will decision about whether or not to participate, the researcher made sure to provide all potential respondents with all pertinent information about the study's purpose, the risks and benefits of participating, the length of the study, contact information, and assurances about participating.

Health and Safety Protocols. The researcher made sure that the health protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) were appropriately observed when the researcher conducted the study to ensure the researcher's safety as well as the safety of the respondents and other individuals involved in the study.

Data Privacy. One of the most important ethical considerations is the confidentiality of the information or the data privacy provided by the respondents. Any information related to respondents or provided by the respondents cannot be made available or accessed by anyone other than the researcher under any circumstances. The information given would not be used to protect the respondents from outside threats. Moreover, confidentiality ensures that respondents' identifying information is not mentioned in the research reports or other published documents. The respondents were always referred to as anonymous in the research presentation.

Legally, a researcher cannot ask questions other than those related to the research purpose. The respondents have the right to walk out of the research if they feel any violation of information accessibility. Therefore, it is always suggested that the researchers use as simple research methods as possible and explain everything in detail to the respondents in order to prevent consequences for transgressing ethical standards.

Therefore, the respondents were not bothered about keeping the information because the data collected stayed with the researcher. Also, the identities of the respondents were kept confidential. The proper health protocol was followed before going to the sample respondents.

Voluntary Participation. All research respondents are free to participate without pressure or coercion. Participation is voluntary, and participants may withdraw from or leave the study at any point without feeling an obligation to continue. The expectation that the researcher ensured the necessary implications forms for consent practices—that is, that the respondents were fully informed about the procedures and risks involved in research and that they must give their consent—is, according to the researcher, one of the most fundamental ethical considerations in research.

Cultural Sensitivity. The researcher thought beyond race and ethnicity. As we all know, different people hold different views about politeness depending on their culture. Culture-specific politeness norms are cultural perceptions of appropriateness in communication, safeguarding communication from threatening acts, and people employing politeness norms. Some cultures preferred positive, while others prefer negative politeness strategies. In this way, politeness is culturally bound. Either way, both contributed to the success of

the study.

Recruitment. The respondents were informed of why they had become part of the study. The researcher explained the study's goal to facilitate additional inferences and enable the respondents to grasp the substance of the study. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained the relevance and reasoning for the study.

Risks. Research was conducted to determine if there was an acceptable positive benefit-risk ratio. This study's needed to protect the respondents from significant harm was equally essential. The study prioritized the welfare of the respondents. Furthermore, the respondents were not harmed since their identity was held confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern. As the researcher, it was needed to ensure that the respondents were physically, emotionally, and socially ready. In answering the survey questionnaire, the researcher provided the respondents did not feel discomfort or awkwardness.

Benefits. This research study was significant for the following reasons: First, for global significance, this research was a realization for all people around the world of how self-concept and emotional intelligence affect teacher performance. School administration can see the bigger picture in line with the self-concept and emotional intelligence of the respondents, then eventually come up with possible solutions to problems embodied in the policies they will craft.

Moreover, teachers should be conscious of the hidden curriculum, such as the impact of self-concept and emotional intelligence, which affect teachers' teaching performance, and they might act to improve the situation. Also, it might help learners thoroughly understand the importance of self-concept and emotional intelligence of teachers concerning teaching performance. The study may help advance their knowledge of people, especially those involved in this study. This study can be used as a reference for other researchers. Thus, it may serve as reading material but also as a channel for awakening the persons involved. This study helped the community be aware of this implicit factor in teachers' teaching performance.

Plagiarism. There was no hint or proof that the research had misinterpreted someone else's work. It was run via plagiarism detection programs such as Grammarly. Cheerful character and integrity, linked to moral characteristics and ideals, are essential for researchers. To produce a respectable research report, the researcher must be more knowledgeable about plagiarism.

Fabrication. There was no hint or evidence in the report that the work had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of information or outcomes, nor was there deliberate presentation of incorrect conclusions. The investigator utilized and incorporated ideas associated with the data and other inferential notions.

Falsification. There was no indication that the study overstated or exaggerated anything, nor did it deliberately falsify the data to meet a model or theoretical assumption. Additionally, this study needed to be more compliant with data manipulation, which included making claims or omitting crucial information and utilizing supplies, equipment, or techniques that could mislead others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). There were no signs of a conflict of interest in the study, including the disclosure of one. A conflict of interest is a collection of situations in which a professional's assessment of a primary interest—such as the well-being of respondents or the reliability of the research—is likely to be impacted by a secondary interest—such as financial or intellectual gains or recognitions. Furthermore, the researcher, who had no authority or influence over the respondents, forced them to take part in the survey.

Deceit. The study did not mislead the respondents about any possible danger. Study participants must have their rights enormously safeguarded, mainly since they have completed higher education; hence, reasonable and acceptable guidelines must be followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The study's researcher adhered to protocol. Following the go-ahead from the panels, advisor, and RMMC ERC committee, the researcher formally requested permission from the superintendents of the school divisions to perform the study in a letter. Following this, the researcher composed an official letter and attached the school's letter of support from the superintendent of the school division to the District Supervisor and Principals of the participating schools in the study. The teacher-respondents who were part of the study were oriented before administering the survey questionnaires.

Authorship. Ethical authorship entails ensuring that all individuals contributing substantially to the research are appropriately acknowledged as authors. In contrast, those who do not meet the criteria for authorship are not included. The researcher ensured that the study's results appropriately reflected the contributions of all parties involved and were fair and transparent. Research outputs maintained their credibility and made a fair and transparent contribution to the progress of knowledge by abiding by ethical authoring norms.

Results

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets data on self-fulfillment, honesty, autonomy, emotional self-concept, teaching effectiveness, and emotional intelligence in terms of self-awareness, emotion management, self-motivation, empathy, and social skills.

3.1. The Level of Self-Concept among TLE Teachers

Table 2 presents the level of self-concept among TLE teachers in terms of self-fulfillment, honesty, autonomy, and emotional self-concept. Mean and description were utilized to treat the data gathered.

The data revealed that TLE teachers had a high level of self-concept in terms of self-fulfillment, as indicated by a mean score of 4.0, which reflects agreement. These teachers expressed satisfaction with their achievements in life, with a mean score of 4.1. Furthermore, they reported accomplishing important goals they had set for themselves, with a mean score of 3.9. However, they have not achieved anything significant, as indicated by a mean score of 4.4. Nevertheless, TLE teachers consistently overcome difficulties, with a mean score of 4.2. If given the chance to start their lives over, they would make minimal changes, as reflected by a mean score of 3.8. Finally, these teachers feel proud of how they manage their lives, with a mean score of 3.5.

Regarding honesty, TLE teachers displayed a high level of self-concept, as evidenced by a mean score of 4.1, indicating agreement. They were regarded as trustworthy individuals, with a mean score of 4.3, and known to keep their word, with a mean score of 4.1. TLE teachers were considered decent and honest individuals, as reflected by a mean score of 4.1. They consciously avoided actions that could harm others, with a mean score of 4.0, and held their promises in high regard, with a mean score of 4.0.

Table 2. The Level of Self-Concept among TLE Teachers

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Self-Fulfillment	4.0	High
Honesty	4.1	High
Autonomy	3.0	Moderately High
Emotional Self-Concept	3.9	High

Regarding autonomy, TLE teachers exhibited a moderately high level of self-concept, with a mean score of 3.0, indicating a fair degree of agreement. They acknowledged a greater dependence on others than most people they knew, as indicated by a mean score of 3.0. When initiating any action, they felt the need for approval from others first, with a mean score of 3.6. TLE teachers found it challenging to embark on endeavors without the support of others, as reflected by a mean score of 2.9. They heavily relied on others' opinions when making decisions, with a mean score of 2.5. TLE teachers had difficulty making independent decisions, with a mean score of 3.0.

Concerning emotional self-concept, TLE teachers exhibited a high level of self-concept, as indicated by a mean score of 3.9, reflecting agreement. They found it challenging to recover quickly when feeling down, with a mean score of 4.1. TLE teachers perceived themselves as uptight and highly strung, with a mean score of 3.9. They considered themselves more sensitive than most, as reflected by a mean score of 3.5. However, they also identified as emotionally resilient individuals, with a mean score of 4.2. While they experienced significant distress when things went wrong, as indicated by a mean score of 4.0, they demonstrated knowledge of self-care strategies to minimize suffering, with a mean score of 3.4.

3.2. The Level of Teaching Performance of TLE Teachers

Table 3 shows the degree of pedagogy and content knowledge that TLE teachers possess, as well as their performance in terms of learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, professional engagement and community links, and personal and professional development. Mean and description were utilized to treat the data gathered.

The data reveals that TLE teachers demonstrate high teaching performance in various areas. In content knowledge and pedagogy, teachers display a strong understanding and application of the curriculum, with a mean score of 3.9. They effectively utilize research-based teaching methods to enhance their professional practice, with a mean score of 3.4. TLE teachers demonstrate proficiency in using language (Mother et al.) to facilitate teaching and learning, with a mean score of 4.7. They employ effective verbal and non-verbal strategies to support student understanding, engagement, and achievement, with a mean score of 3.6. Teachers also employ diverse teaching strategies to promote critical and creative thinking, with a mean score of 3.3.

TLE teachers excel in creating a conducive learning environment, with a mean score of 4.4. They establish safe and inclusive learning spaces, maintain fairness and respect, and manage classrooms effectively for meaningful exploration and hands-on activities, with mean scores ranging from 4.1 to 4.8. Teachers use strategies that motivate learners to take responsibility for their learning, with a mean score of 4.5. They also manage student behavior constructively, with a mean score of 4.2.

Table 3. The Level of Teaching Performance of TLE Teachers

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.9	High
Learning Environment	4.4	High
Diversity of Learners	3.4	Moderately High
Curriculum and Planning	3.4	Moderately High
Assessment and Reporting	4.2	High
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	3.9	High
Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.5	High

Regarding the diversity of learners, TLE teachers demonstrate a moderately high level of teaching performance, with a mean score of 3.4. They provide differentiated and culturally responsive learning experiences, address learners' needs and backgrounds, and design teaching strategies for learners with disabilities and exceptional circumstances.

Teaching performance is moderately high in terms of curriculum and planning, with a mean score of 3.4. TLE teachers effectively plan

and implement developmentally appropriate teaching and learning processes, set achievable learning outcomes, and adapt learning programs to meet the needs of all learners. They also engage in collegial discussions and utilize appropriate teaching resources, including ICT.

In assessment and reporting, TLE teachers demonstrate a high level of teaching performance, with a mean score of 4.2. They design and implement assessment strategies aligned with the curriculum, monitor and evaluate learner progress, provide timely and constructive feedback, and effectively communicate learners' needs and achievements to stakeholders. Teachers also utilize assessment data to inform instructional modifications and program improvements.

Teaching performance regarding community linkages and professional engagement is high, with a mean score of 3.9. TLE teachers maintain learning environments responsive to community contexts and consistently implement school policies and procedures to foster positive relationships with learners, parents, and stakeholders.

Finally, regarding personal growth and professional development, teaching performance is high, with a mean score of 3.5. TLE teachers adopt learner-centered philosophies, uphold professionalism through caring, respect, and integrity, and actively participate in professional networks. They also develop personal professional improvement plans based on reflective practice and ongoing learning.

3.3. The Level of Emotional Intelligence among TLE Teachers

Table 4 presents the level of emotional intelligence among TLE teachers in terms of self-awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself, empathy, and social skills. Mean and description were utilized to treat the data gathered.

The data analysis revealed that TLE teachers demonstrated high emotional intelligence, particularly in self-awareness. The mean score of 3.8 indicates that teachers generally agreed with their ability to recognize and understand their emotions. They displayed prompt awareness when they lost their temper (mean of 4.2) or felt happy (mean of 4.5). Additionally, teachers showed a good sense of recognizing their stress levels (mean of 4.3) and being aware when they were emotionally affected (mean of 4.5). While they were able to identify the reasons behind their anxiety (mean of 3.5), teachers acknowledged that they sometimes struggled to recognize when they were being unreasonable (mean of 2.1). Nevertheless, overall self-awareness remained significant to them (mean of 3.7), as they could also identify when someone upset or annoyed them (mean of 4.3) and release anger quickly (mean of 2.4). Furthermore, teachers had a firm grasp of their sources of happiness (mean of 4.7).

Regarding the management of emotions, TLE teachers demonstrated a moderately high level of emotional intelligence with a mean score of 3.4. They could quickly reframe negative situations (mean of 2.4) and did not openly display their emotions (mean of 3.9). Others found it difficult to discern their current mood (mean of 3.4), as teachers rarely lost their temper with people (mean of 3.7). Challenging individuals did not easily irritate them (mean of 2.1), and they consciously altered their mindset or mood when necessary (mean of 4.0). While teachers aimed to prevent work-related stress from affecting their personal lives (mean of 3.1), they occasionally struggled with worrying about work or life in general (mean of 4.6). They were also capable of suppressing their emotions when required (mean of 3.5), and others often found it challenging to determine their emotional state (mean of 3.1).

Regarding self-motivation, TLE teachers displayed a high level of emotional intelligence with a mean score of 3.7, indicating agreement. They consistently motivated themselves to tackle complex tasks (mean of 4.6) and effectively prioritized important activities (mean of 4.3). Meeting deadlines was not always a strong suit (mean of 2.3), but they rarely spent time (mean of 3.5) or procrastinated (mean of 3.5). Teachers recognized the importance of addressing complex tasks first (mean of 2.4) and valued delayed gratification (mean of 3.6). "Action this Day" was a principle they embraced (mean of 3.5), and they maintained self-motivation even during low periods (mean of 4.5). They attributed their success to their motivation (mean of 4.6).

Table 4. *The Level of Emotional Intelligence among TLE Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Self-Awareness	3.8	High
Managing Emotions	3.4	Moderately High
Motivating Oneself	3.7	High
Empathy	3.8	High
Social Skills	4.5	Very High

Regarding empathy, TLE teachers exhibited high emotional intelligence, as indicated by a mean score of 3.8, showing agreement. They consistently saw things from others' perspectives (mean of 3.4) and excelled at empathizing with others' problems (mean of 4.3). Teachers were skilled at discerning if someone was unhappy with them (mean of 4.5) or if there was discord within a team (mean of 3.4). While they generally understood the reasons behind others' challenging behavior (mean of 2.5), they acknowledged that individuals were not inherently tricky but somewhat different (mean of 4.1). Teachers also recognized when they were being unreasonable (mean of 4.5) and understood how their actions might unintentionally offend others (mean of 4.3). Although they could sometimes see things from others' perspectives (mean of 3.5), the reasons for disagreements were unclear (mean of 3.3).

Lastly, concerning social skills, TLE teachers displayed a very high level of emotional intelligence, with a mean score of 4.5, indicating substantial agreement. They excelled as active listeners (mean of 4.9) and avoided interrupting others' conversations (mean of 4.4).

These teachers displayed adaptability and a knack for engaging with a diverse range of individuals (mean of 4.3). People generally fascinated them (mean of 4.1), and they enjoyed meeting new individuals and understanding what drove them (mean of 4.8). Various colleagues made their jobs more enjoyable (mean of 3.9) and actively sought information to understand what was important to others (mean of 4.4). They viewed working with difficult people as a challenge to overcome (mean of 4.5) and demonstrated skill in reconciling differences (mean of 4.6), thus fostering strong relationships in the workplace (mean of 4.7).

3.4. Significant Relationship Between Self-Concept and Emotional Intelligence of TLE Teachers

The significant correlation between self-concept and emotional intelligence of TLE teachers is displayed in Table 5. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used to handle the collected data.

When the self-concept and emotional intelligence of TLE teachers were measured, it was discovered that the data were measured at the 122 df alpha level, or.05. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.79, as the table demonstrates. The null hypothesis was rejected because it was more than 0.170. The teacher's self-concept highly impacted the level of emotional intelligence.

Table 5. Significant Relationship between Self-concept and Emotional Intelligence

Variables	Df	rxy value		Decision	Analysis
		n=124			
		Computed	Tabular		
Self-Concept					
Vs.	122	0.79	0.170	Reject null hypothesis	There was a significant relationship.
Emotional Intelligence					

3.5. Significant Relationship Between Teaching Performance and Emotional Intelligence of TLE Teachers

The significant correlation between teaching performance and emotional intelligence of TLE teachers is displayed in Table 6. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was employed to handle the collected data.

When the teaching performance and emotional intelligence of TLE teachers were measured, it was discovered that the data were measured at the 122 df alpha level, or.05. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.81, as the table demonstrates. The null hypothesis was rejected because it was more than 0.170. The teacher's teaching performance highly impacted the level of emotional intelligence.

Table 6. Significant Relationship between Teaching Performance and Emotional Intelligence

Variables	Df	rxy value		Decision	Analysis
		n=124			
		Computed	Tabular		
Teaching Performance					
Vs.	122	0.81	0.170	Reject null hypothesis	There was a significant relationship.
Emotional Intelligence					

3.5. Domain of Self-Concept and Teaching Performance Significantly Predict Emotional Intelligence

Table 7 presents the self-concept domain, and teaching performance significantly predicts emotional intelligence. Since the probability value is $p < 0.05$. R² value of .531 implies that 53.1% of the self-concept and teaching performance best predicts teachers' emotional intelligence, while other factors influenced the remaining 47.9%. It revealed that the t-values of self-concept regarding self-fulfillment, honesty, autonomy, and emotional self-concept were 2.15, 3.105, 1.009, and 3.478, respectively. It further showed that the t-values for teaching performance were 2.786, 1.44, 1.983, 3.541, 1.49, 3.105, and 1.44 for content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, community links and professional engagement, and personal growth and professional development, in that order.

These values indicate that specific aspects of teaching performance, such as curriculum and planning, community linkages, and professional engagement, have a strong predictive relationship with emotional intelligence.

Therefore, among the four indicators of self-concept, emotional self-concept emerged as the strongest predictor of teachers' emotional intelligence, with a significant probability value of $p < 0.05$. This finding underscores the critical role of emotional self-concept in

shaping a teacher's emotional intelligence, suggesting that how teachers perceive and manage their emotions significantly influences their overall emotional intelligence. Thus, curriculum and planning were the best predictors of emotional intelligence, with a coefficient of 3.541 and a highly significant p-value of 0.001. Effective curriculum planning substantially impacts teachers' emotional intelligence, highlighting its importance in fostering academic success and emotional development.

Table 7. *Domain of Self-Concept and Teaching Performance Significantly Predict Emotional Intelligence*

<i>Self-Concept</i>	<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>		
	<i>B</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Self-Fulfillment	.203	2.15	.005
Honesty	.201	3.105	.003
Autonomy	.170	1.009	.105
Emotional Self-Concept	.279	3.478	.002
Teaching Performance			
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	.214	2.786	.003
Learning Environment	.07	1.44	2.540
Diversity of Learners	.252	1.983	.002
Curriculum and Planning	.690	3.541	.001
Assessment and Reporting	.61	1.49	2.85
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	.201	3.105	.003
Personal Growth and Professional Development	.85	1.44	2.09
R	.804		
R-square	.531		
F-value	108.12		
P-value	.000		

Discussion

This section discusses the data on TLE teachers' self-concept, teaching performance, and emotional intelligence.

The Level of Self-Concept among TLE Teachers

The level of self-concept among TLE teachers was agreed upon in terms of self-fulfillment, autonomy, and emotional self-concept, while sometimes they agreed on autonomy.

The self-concept of TLE teachers reflected a high level of self-fulfillment. These teachers have made significant accomplishments, overcome challenges, and take pride in managing their lives effectively. They would stay the same if given the chance to start over, indicating a sense of contentment and satisfaction. However, it is noteworthy that TLE teachers still feel they still need to achieve specific goals. This finding aligns with a study conducted by Alibakhshi et al. (2018), which defines self-concept as a comprehensive term encompassing an individual's mental and physical characteristics and their evaluation of these attributes. The concept encompasses three dimensions: cognitive, affective, and behavioral. Moreover, self-concept involves self-awareness, encompassing the development of self-image, ideal self, and self-esteem.

On the other hand, the self-concept of TLE teachers reflected a high level of honesty. These teachers view themselves as individuals who prioritize integrity and strive not to harm others. Their promises hold significant value, and they consider themselves decent and honest. This observation aligns with a study conducted by Devos et al. (2021), which defines teacher self-concept as teachers' self-perceptions of their teaching effectiveness. The study highlights the importance of teachers' beliefs in their competence, often called self-efficacy or self-concept, as these beliefs can influence various psychological aspects of teaching. Thus, it is crucial for teacher education programs to foster positive teaching self-concepts, not only as a primary objective but also as a crucial factor that positively impacts other desirable outcomes in teaching contexts. Including elements that enhance self-concept in teacher education programs can lead to sustainable benefits and effectively prepare teachers to teach.

Moreover, the self-concept of TLE teachers demonstrated a moderately high level of autonomy. These teachers find it moderately challenging to make decisions independently and rely on the support and opinions of others before taking action. They perceive themselves as depending on others more than most people they know. This finding corresponds to the study conducted by Trigwell et al. (2019), which emphasizes the teacher's professional self-concept and self-esteem as crucial aspects of their generalized image or implicit theory of themselves as professionals. The perception of oneself as a competent communicator plays a vital role in the teacher's self-concept, as effective teaching relies on high-quality pedagogical communication.

Regarding emotional self-concept, TLE teachers exhibited a high level of difficulty in snapping out of low moods. They perceive themselves as uptight and highly-strung individuals who believe they are more sensitive than most. When faced with adversity, they tend to suffer significantly. However, they also consider themselves emotionally resilient and possess the ability to take care of themselves to avoid prolonged suffering. This observation aligns with the study of Turner and Stough (2020), which explores the effectiveness of professional communication with students based on teachers' communicative culture. This culture consists of internal

components related to teachers' communicative competencies and external components related to their modes of behavior in different pedagogical situations. Teachers' professional self-concept can be evaluated based on their perception of their communicative competencies and their image of their communicative behavior.

The Level of Teaching Performance of TLE Teachers

The level of teaching performance of TLE teachers agreed upon in content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, assessment and reporting, community linkages, professional engagement, and personal growth and professional development, while sometimes agreeing on the diversity of learners and curriculum and planning.

TLE teachers' teaching performance demonstrated a high proficiency in content knowledge and pedagogy. These teachers possess applied knowledge in curriculum teaching areas and effectively utilize research-based principles of teaching and learning to enhance their professional practice. They demonstrated proficient communication skills in their Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English, facilitating learning through effective verbal and non-verbal classroom strategies. Their teaching strategies support learners' understanding, engagement, and achievement, fostering the development of critical and creative thinking skills. This observation aligns with the study conducted by Marsh et al. (2019), which highlights the prevalence of teacher performance evaluations in public elementary schools. The findings indicate that formal evaluations are a common practice, emphasizing the significance of assessing teaching performance.

Moreover, TLE teachers excelled in creating a high-quality learning environment. They establish safe and secure learning environments by consistently implementing policies and procedures. These teachers promote fairness, respect, and care, encouraging learning and meaningful engagement in individual and group activities. They maintain supportive learning environments that inspire learners to participate, cooperate, collaborate, and take responsibility for their learning. Positive and non-violent discipline strategies are applied to ensure learning-focused environments. These findings parallel the study by Lych et al. (2018), highlighting the evaluation procedures employed to assess various aspects of teaching performance, often concluding with feedback or written reports on the outcomes.

Regarding the diversity of learners, TLE teachers demonstrated a moderately high level of proficiency. They employ differentiated and developmentally appropriate learning experiences that consider learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences. These teachers establish a learner-centered culture that respects learners' linguistic, cultural, socio-economic, and religious backgrounds. They design teaching strategies responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness, talents, and those facing challenging circumstances. To further meet the requirements of students from indigenous communities, they modify and use culturally relevant teaching techniques. This observation aligns with the study conducted by Abdullah and Aslam (2020), emphasizing the critical role teachers play in the educational system and the direct impact of teacher performance on student learning and achievement.

Regarding curriculum and planning, TLE teachers exhibited a moderately high level of proficiency. They set achievable and appropriate learning outcomes aligned with learning competencies, ensuring the relevance and responsiveness of learning programs to meet the needs of all learners. These teachers actively participate in collegial discussions and utilize teacher and learner feedback to enrich their teaching practice. They select, develop, organize, and employ suitable teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals effectively. This finding corresponds to the study conducted by Roche and Marsh (2020), which highlights the impact of stress on teachers' performance and the significance of personal and professional resources as buffers against the adverse effects of stress.

Further, TLE teachers excel in assessment and reporting practices. They monitor and evaluate learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data, providing timely, accurate, and constructive feedback to improve learner performance. These teachers promptly communicate learners' needs, progress, and achievements to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians. They utilize assessment data to modify teaching and learning practices and programs. This observation aligns with the study conducted by MacArthur et al. (2020), emphasizing the importance of teachers' performance and expertise in the educational system, particularly in light of the K to 12 Basic Education Program in the Philippines.

The Level of Emotional Intelligence of TLE Teachers

TLE teachers' emotional intelligence level strongly agreed with empathy and social skills, with self-awareness and motivating oneself, and sometimes with managing emotions.

TLE teachers' teaching performance demonstrated a high proficiency in content knowledge and pedagogy. These teachers possess applied knowledge in curriculum teaching areas and effectively utilize research-based principles of teaching and learning to enhance their professional practice. They demonstrate proficient communication skills in their Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English, facilitating learning through effective verbal and non-verbal classroom strategies. Their teaching strategies support learners' understanding, engagement, and achievement, fostering the development of critical and creative thinking skills. This observation aligns with the study conducted by Marsh et al. (2019), which highlights the prevalence of teacher performance evaluations in public elementary schools. The findings indicate that formal evaluations are a common practice, emphasizing the significance of assessing teaching performance.

TLE teachers excel in creating a high-quality learning environment. They establish safe and secure learning environments by consistently implementing policies and procedures. These teachers promote fairness, respect, and care, encouraging learning and

meaningful engagement in individual and group activities. They maintain supportive learning environments that inspire learners to participate, cooperate, collaborate, and take responsibility for their learning. These findings parallel the study by Lych et al. (2018), highlighting the evaluation procedures employed to assess various aspects of teaching performance, often concluding with feedback or written reports on the outcomes.

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Significant Relationship Between Self-Concept and Emotional Intelligence of TLE Teachers

When the self-concept and emotional intelligence of TLE teachers were measured, it was discovered that the data were measured at the 122 df alpha level, or .05. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.79, as the table demonstrates. The null hypothesis was rejected since it was higher than the tabular value 0.170. The teacher's self-concept highly impacted the level of emotional intelligence. Furthermore, teachers with emotional intelligence are skilled at recognizing and managing their students' emotions. They can identify when students may be experiencing difficulties, stress, or emotional distress and provide appropriate support and guidance. They create opportunities for students to develop emotional awareness and regulation skills, promoting social-emotional learning and well-being (McArthur et al., 2020; Maksimović & Osmanović, 2019).

Significant Relationship Between Teaching Performance and Emotional Intelligence of TLE Teachers

When the teaching performance and emotional intelligence of TLE teachers were measured, it was discovered that the data were measured at the 122 df alpha level, or .05. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.81, as the table demonstrates. The null hypothesis was rejected because it was more than 0.170. The teacher's teaching performance highly impacted the level of emotional intelligence.

However, before encouraging emotional intelligence in their students, educators must first cultivate emotional intelligence in themselves. To achieve that, teachers must assess themselves by looking at their strengths and weaknesses as educators. In addition to being self-aware, an emotionally intelligent teacher will also show empathy and compassion. An educator with emotional intelligence is well-versed in improving classroom management. He/she can deal with different issues of children more healthily (Arghode et al., 2022; Kusumaningrum et al., 2019).

Domain of Self-Concept and Teaching Performance Significantly Predict Emotional Intelligence

Among the four indicators in self-concept, the best domain that significantly predicts teachers' emotional intelligence was emotional self-concept with $p < 0.05$. The best domain that significantly predicts teachers' emotional intelligence regarding teaching performance was curriculum and planning, with a coefficient of 3.541 and $p = .001$, which is less than a 0.05 significance level. Managed teachers' emotions are crucial to fostering a positive and productive learning environment. Like any other professional, teachers experience a range of emotions that can significantly impact their effectiveness in the classroom. Creating a supportive and empathetic school culture is critical in managing teachers' emotions. School leaders should encourage open communication and provide a platform for teachers to express their feelings and concerns.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: First, the level of self-concept of TLE teachers was high in terms of self-fulfillment, honesty, and emotional self-concept, while moderately high with regards to autonomy. Second, the level of

teaching performance of TLE teachers was high in relation to the content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, assessment and reporting, community linkages and professional engagement, and personal growth and professional development, while moderately high in diversity of learners and curriculum and planning. Third, the level of emotional intelligence of TLE teachers was very high in terms of social skills, while high in self-awareness, motivating oneself, and empathy while moderately high in terms of managing emotions.

Fourth, there was a significant relationship between self-concept and emotional intelligence, as well as between teaching performance and emotional intelligence. Lastly, it was found out that the domain of self-concept that significantly predicted teachers' emotional intelligence was emotional self-concept. While, the domain that best predicted teachers' emotional intelligence regarding teaching performance was curriculum and planning

The school administrator may use the results of this study to see the bigger picture in accordance with the participants' self-concept and emotional intelligence, then eventually come up with possible solutions to problems that are embodied in the policies that they are going to craft. Teachers may be conscious of the hidden curriculum, such as the impact of self-concept and emotional intelligence on teachers' teaching performance, and they might act to improve the situation.

Moreover, it might help the learners understand thoroughly the importance of self-concept and emotional intelligence of teachers concerning teaching performance. The study may help future researchers advance their knowledge of people, especially the people involved in this study. This study can be used as a reference for other researchers. Thus, it may serve as reading material but also as a channel for awakening the persons involved. This study could help the community be aware of this implicit factor in teachers' teaching performance.

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